

Enabling Discoveries in Heliospheric Science through Laboratory Plasma Experiments

White paper for the Heliophysics 2050 workshop

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Introduction:

Recent results from today's most advanced multi-spacecraft missions (MMS, Cluster) suggest that the physics of reconnection, shocks, and turbulence are distinctly three-dimensional. While these and proposed missions such as HelioSwarm and CrossScale seek to understand the 3D and multiscale physics via a constellation of satellites, such spacecraft missions are limited: they only allow exploration of naturally occurring solar wind plasmas, lack control over the plasma parameters, are unable to track the evolution of the plasma, and can not distinguish whether the observations are due to local effects or variations in the initial conditions. Similarly, tackling these 3D and multi-scale phenomena with simulations is a steep challenge. Even if computing capabilities continue advancing at the rate of the recent decades, simulations in 2050 will remain unable to fully resolve all naturally occurring heliophysics phenomena, particularly in three spatial dimensions.¹ The additional computational complexity of the appropriate model choice across this wide range of temporal and spatial scales, e.g., the need for kinetic modeling of the collisionless solar wind, only makes the limitations of computing more salient.

Laboratory experiments have a demonstrated ability to investigate both the 3D and multi-scale nature of heliospheric phenomena, complementing the limitations of spacecraft and simulations. While laboratory experiments may have raw densities and temperatures that differ from those that arise naturally in space and astrophysical plasmas, when normalized to the appropriate plasma parameters, laboratory experiments operate well within the regimes relevant to space and astrophysical plasmas. While the raw collision rate in existing laboratory plasma experiments is much higher than in the solar wind and magnetosphere, the time between collisions can be much slower than the physics of interest, and still allow the study of kinetic physics in collisionless systems relevant to heliospheric science. The range of normalized plasma parameters accessible to laboratory plasma experiments also allow the study of fluid physics in relevant heliospheric regimes.

Laboratory experiments have a number of benefits - they can simulate regions inaccessible to spacecraft, such as coronal loops on the surface of the Sun (M. Haw APJ 2018). They can take multi-point measurements of systems at scales beyond the capabilities of the spacecraft clusters, such as plasmoids in the heliospheric current sheet (E. Peterson Nat Phys 2019). They can probe

¹ Continuing at the Moore's law pace of the past 40 years, by 2050 we would at most expect to have zetta-scale (1e21 flops/second) supercomputers, and have the capability of performing Reynolds number $\sim 10^5$ - 10^6 fluid calculations at uniform resolution. Even with algorithmic advances such as adaptive mesh refinement, the equivalent magnetohydrodynamic simulations would still be orders of magnitude off from the real resistivity of heliospheric systems such as the solar corona. Thus, we cannot expect direct numerical simulations of these plasma systems to completely supplant other means of advancing our understanding of the heliosphere.

fundamental physics interactions relevant to the heliosphere, such as nonlinear interactions between counterpropagating Alfvén waves (G. Howes PRL 2012 and D. Drake PoP 2013). They can explore physical processes that are outside the range of current theoretical models, such as collisionless plasmoids observed below the ion kinetic scale (J. Olson PRL 2016). They can also uncover physical processes that were not originally expected from theoretical models (S. Dorfman PRL 2016). They have even been used to investigate the reliability of spacecraft measurements (J Yoo JGR 2012 and J. Schroeder PoP 2017). A successful Helio2050 community will take full advantage of laboratory experiments to address questions unresolvable by simulations or spacecraft measurements alone.

Vision for the Helio2050 State of the Field:

For a researcher looking to execute a heliophysics relevant experiment today, several user facilities exist, including UCLA's LArge Plasma Device (LAPD), Wisconsin Plasma Physics Lab's (WiPPL's) Big Red Ball (BRB), Rochester's Laboratory for Laser Energetics (LLE), and Auburn's Magnetized Plasma Research Laboratory (MPRL), as well as the DIII-D Frontier Science Campaign. Together, these platforms provide a reasonable coverage of space and astrophysical plasma parameters and produce a great deal of excellent research. However, it is difficult for researchers without a background in experimental plasma physics to effectively use these tools. Improving facility accessibility means not only soliciting users with a wide variety of backgrounds, but also creating training opportunities and providing staff support to allow those users to succeed. For this reason, our vision for the state of the field in 2050 requires continued funding and improvement along two main channels:

- **Increased funding for both human and physical infrastructure development** so that these facilities can operate more effectively as user facilities, continually expand the explorable parameter space, and ensure equitable access for all potential users, particularly those from a diverse range of institutions
- **Creating an educated workforce** that optimizes use of laboratory experiments as a tool for investigating space and astrophysical plasma physics questions

Increased funding for both human and physical infrastructure development

Robust collaboration between laboratory, computation, and in-situ measurements happens with dedicated support and focus from the community.

Short term: Increased funding for the creation of dedicated scientist positions to broaden access to these facilities and specifically facilitate connections to NASA missions.

A user facility requires investment both in the physical infrastructure (in the form of robust equipment and control processes, developing the ability to access data easily, etc.) as well as time on helping potential users design and run experiments on the machine. NASA has dozens of staff doing this for each spacecraft mission, and NIF and OMEGA similarly have a number of scientists in this role, whereas most laboratory plasma facilities only have a handful of dedicated staff. Adding additional dedicated scientist positions will allow more science to be done by a more diverse group of users, as well as allowing more time to be dedicated to improving the machine's physical infrastructure, benefiting all users. Bringing in additional scientists that can both improve infrastructure and devote time specifically to science relevant to NASA missions, will allow a deeper understanding of the phenomena observed by the spacecraft.

Long term: Dedicated funding sources to allow professors and graduate students to develop experiments at their home institutions to run on the user facilities. This has been the practice in laser facilities for many years, providing grants for specific experiments to bring to the user facility. Implemented broadly, this would open pathways for starting and maintaining experimental plasma physics laboratories at a diverse set of institutions, including small liberal arts colleges and historically black colleges and universities (HBCU). For example, designing and building one additional piece of equipment to simulate the Sun and the Parker Spiral (and support the ongoing missions of Parker Solar Probe and Solar Orbiter) using the existing diagnostics on a machine, is relatively inexpensive but can yield incredible scientific results. It is important to ensure that any dedicated pool of funds for approved users at these facilities include the option to apply for salary support for the personnel involved to conduct the work. In addition to funding the salaries of undergraduates, graduate students and postdocs, running an experimental lab requires money to purchase materials and equipment. By providing a dedicated funding source, this would encourage the growth of small plasma physics groups at diverse institutions. Along with continued support, an important part of maintaining the usefulness of laboratory experiments over the next thirty years will involve **the investment in new user facilities** to expand both the parameter regimes available and the range of scales that can be captured.

Creating an educated workforce

Education is a vital part of ensuring that early career scientists are poised to take advantage of existing user facilities. Developing educational tools to teach students and postdocs about the potential of laboratory experiments, and training them to design their own experiments, is necessary to maximize their use. To this end, we recommend:

Creating a summer school to educate students and postdocs on how to implement their research question in laboratory experiments. This would educate graduate students and postdocs on the capabilities of the facilities and the process for designing an experiment, with the ultimate goal of running their own proposed experiments. In the **short term**, this would be for older graduate students and postdocs with specific research areas of interest. In the **long term**, this could be extended to younger graduate students and undergraduate students. This proposed summer school would involve scientists from LAPD, WIPPL, and the laser facilities. These facilities together cover a range of parameters that includes questions of interest to most space and astrophysical scientists. It could also include training in basic plasma physics, an opportunity not available to students at smaller institutions with a limited plasma presence, and eventually be extended to available computational tools as well. These summer schools will ensure that students at all institutions have access to user facilities, training in diverse codes, and opportunities to innovatively collaborate with peers apart from their institutional advisors. These connections with peers will form the seed for future collaborations and research projects. The intentional professional development of the SHINE conference for young heliophysics scientists serves as an example of the significant benefits provided to early career scientists and the field from such an investment.

Creation of a summer lab program along the lines of the Office of Science Graduate Student Research (SCGSR) Program or Summer Undergraduate Laboratory Internship (SULI). This would be another channel to support students and professors at smaller institutions in creating and maintaining a robust laboratory experiment program.